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Contributions of Metacognition to Creative Performance and Behavior

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Abstract

How are ideas born? Contrary to commonly held beliefs, creative performance, like any goal-oriented action, requires understanding and managing one's own cognitive processes – thus, efficient metacognition. Recently, a systematic framework of creative metacognition has been proposed, assuming the relevance of metacognitive knowledge, monitoring, and control in creative performance. Here, we provide the first comprehensive empirical examination of this conception. Specifically, an online sample (N= 425) performed DT tasks and gave insight in relevant aspects of metacognitive processes during task performance. The study revealed that all three proposed components of creative metacognition played independent roles in enhancing creative cognitive performance, including divergent thinking (DT) creativity and fluency. Among these components, metacognitive control showed the strongest positive association with creative cognitive performance. As expected, creative metacognition was especially relevant to imminent creative task performance but showed some association with real-life creativity. These findings provide the first empirical evidence that all three postulated components of creative metacognition support creative performance and, to a lesser degree, to creative behavior. In the discussion, we delve deeper into the specific roles of these metacognitive subcomponents in enhancing creative cognitive performance and touch upon the differences between the roles of self-regulation and metacognition in creativity.

Keywords: metacognitive monitoring, metacognitive control, metacognitive knowledge, creative performance, creative behavior, creative activity, creative achievements

Contributions of Metacognition to Creative Performance and Behavior

What makes creativity happen? How do creative ideas arise? There is a widespread belief that they result from free, spontaneous actions and sudden inspiration (Benedek et al., 2021; Lucas & Nordgren, 2022). Although the vision of a breakthrough occurring during everyday routine activities like taking a bath or a nap is encouraging, anyone engaged in creative endeavors — from inventing an original meal with a limited ingredients to more long-term actions like writing a scientific article — knows that creativity is often challenging and requires effort and deliberate management of own resources. In fact, due to the various creative challenges, managing the creative process appears to play an even more significant role than in other more structured activities. The vague criteria of what is deemed creative, the vast solution space typical for such ill-defined problems, and limited opportunities for obtaining feedback imply the need for efficient monitoring and regulation of creative thought. While generating and selecting creative ideas is already a complex task, additional processes may come into play when considering long-term creative endeavors spread out over an extended period (Ivcevic, 2022).

This study examines the factors that support creative performance, specifically metacognition, which we define as thinking about one's own creative thinking (Norman et al., 2019). Recently, a systematic framework of creative metacognition (CMC) has been proposed, formalizing the structure and function of metacognitive processes in creative cognition (Lebuda & Benedek, 2023). Building on available theorizing on metacognition and creativity research, the CMC framework assumes three major metacognitive components—metacognitive knowledge, monitoring and control—involved in creative performance. The present work aims to provide the first empirical examination of these theoretical proposition by testing the independent roles of the three metacognitive components for creative task performance and behavior.

Scope and Structure of Creative Metacognition

The significance of metacognition for creativity has long been emphasized (Armbruster, 1989; Pesut, 1990; Puryear, 2016). One of the most widespread and influential conceptions of metacognition was proposed by Kaufman and Beghetto (2013), who defined it as "a combination of creative self-knowledge (understanding one's own creative strengths and limitations, both within a specific domain and as a general trait) and contextual knowledge (knowing when, where, how, and why to be creative)" (Kaufman & Beghetto, 2013, p. 160). This comprehensive theory connects an individual's perception of own abilities with the socio-cultural context. The approach appears particularly relevant for long-term creative behavior (Diedrich et al., 2018; Lebuda et al., 2021), thus relating to more personality-oriented creative self-regulation: regulating thoughts, emotions and actions (Ivcevic et al., 2023; Zielińska et al., 2023; for further discussion see Lebuda & Benedek 2023). However, creative metacognition, per definition, focuses on managing creative cognition (Dinsmore et al., 2008; Flavell, 1979; Malanchini et al., 2019). Therefore, the recent CMC framework focuses specifically on metacognitive processes that support core cognitive processes in creative cognition (Figure 1).

Figure 1.

Simplified framework of Creative Metacognition (CMC); for the full model, please see Lebuda & Benedek, 2023

The proposed systematic framework of creative metacognition (CMC) builds on advancements in metacognition theory (Ackerman & Thompson, 2017; Flavell, 1979; Nelson & Narens, 1994; Stanovich, 2011) and outlines the structure and function of metacognitive processes in creative cognition such as ideation. The framework comprises of three interplaying components: a relatively more static component of metacognitive knowledge, associated with long-term memory, and two dynamic components of metacognitive control and metacognitive monitoring, which are associated with working memory (Lebuda & Benedek, 2023). Below, we provide a brief description of each component, followed by empirical arguments illustrating how they relate to core cognitive processes and to each other.

CMC knowledge consists of a declarative and procedural knowledge about creative cognition. This includes information about tasks that require creative thinking (metacognitive knowledge at task level, e.g., familiarity the task; Duncker, 1945), strategies specific to resolve creative task (metacognitive knowledge at performance level; Gilhooly et al., 2007), understanding when an idea or product can be considered creative (metacognitive knowledge at response level; for example, can criminal ideas be seen as creative? Kapoor & Kaufman, 2022).

Well-calibrated metacognitive knowledge was shown to bolster idea generation. Learning about the concepts, strategies and criteria of creativity increases fluency and flexibility of divergent thinking (van de Kamp et al., 2015). In fact, knowing relevant indicators of creativity helps to assess creative product more appropriately (Rietzschel et al., 2010). Additionally, a prior experience with divergent thinking enhances the evaluation of creative ideas (van Broekhoven et al., 2022). Thus, the knowledge about cognition supports effective metacognitive monitoring. People who receive feedback during idea generation perform better and generate more original ideas earlier in the process (De Chantal & Organisciak, 2023). It can be assumed that increases in creativity-related knowledge (e.g., learning about what ideas can be considered more vs less creative) may help to better calibrate one's metacognitive monitoring.

CMC monitoring is a set of mental evaluation processes that pertain to effectively judge task characteristics (metacognitive monitoring at task level, e.g., does this task require creativity?), one's own performance in the task (monitoring at performance level; e.g., do ideas come fluently with the current approach?), and assessment of candidate responses (metacognitive monitoring at response level; e.g., is this a creative idea?). A global indicator of metacognitive monitoring is the experience-based judgment of own cognitive actions referred to as metacognitive feelings (Efklides, 2006). In creativity, it reflects the dynamic monitoring of task performance and progress over the course of the task, resulting in feeling of fluency, ease of creative generation, and idea quality (Puente-Díaz, 2023; Puente-Díaz & Cavazos-Arroyo, 2022).

Most of the creative metacognitive monitoring research has focused on the discernment of ideas or assessment of performance (e.g., De Chantal & Organisciak, 2023; Rominger et al., 2022; Sidi et al., 2020; Urban & Urban, 2021). A recent meta-analysis showed that evaluation accuracy is positively related to divergent thinking performance (Guo et al., 2022). More creative people thus appear doubly skilled: they are better at generating ideas and more discerning in idea evaluation (Silvia, 2008). Furthermore,

stimulating the reflection of one's own ideas enhances performance in creative thinking and design tasks (Hao et al., 2016; Wetzstein & Hacker, 2004). It was also found that professional creators tend to engage more in monitoring than lay people (Fayena-Tawil et al., 2011) and their evaluation accuracy improves as they gain experience (Kleinmintz et al., 2014; Kozbelt, 2007). As per the CMC model, monitoring plays a crucial role in boosting creative performance by supporting more informed decision when regulating the creative process, and thereby laying the ground for metacognition control.

CMC control guides the application of core cognitive processes, which includes, among other abilities, the capacity to adapt task performance in response to changing demands. It activated when metacognitive monitoring detects a necessity to make specific decision or to reconsider the current task approach. CMC control is linked to decisions regarding task engagement such as when to start and end task performance (metacognitive control at task level), devising, selecting and changing task strategies (metacognitive control at performance level), and making decisions whether a candidate response should be reported, further elaborated or dismissed (metacognitive control at repose level). People can regulate their creative performance, for example, in accordance with task instructions that either ask to “be creative” or “be fluent” (Acar et al., 2020). Moreover, it has been shown that using more complex cognitive strategies increases the creativity of ideas (Gilhooly et al., 2007; Jia et al., 2022). Additionally, people with higher creative thinking abilities are more likely engage in decision-making and metacognitive control activities, such as making corrections and elaborations (Jankowska et al., 2018).

Based on the concept of procedural metacognition, we assume that the three components of creative metacognition described above dynamically interact (De Chantal & Organisciak, 2023; Nelson & Narens, 1994). Research indicates that based on metacognitive feelings of low fluency resulting from a decreasing number of generated ideas over time, people develop the misconception that their creative performance declines, what leads them to prematurely stop of generating ideas. However, providing knowledge about this phenomenon, thereby improving metacognitive knowledge, counteracts this effect

known as the "creative cliff illusion " (Lucas & Nordgren, 2015, 2020). Hence, metacognitive knowledge can offer insights to better calibrate metacognitive monitoring, and thereby supporting creative process management. This example illustrates the main way in which components of metacognition interact with each other (knowledge calibrating monitoring, which again informs control), and we presume that, similar to the core creative process, creative metacognition is also iterative in nature (Botella et al., 2018; Glaveanu et al., 2013; Rubenstein et al., 2018).

The Present Study

Although the assumptions regarding our metacognition model and its individual structures are derived from recognized metacognition models across various psychology domains and a review of creativity psychology research, only parts of it have been usually tested so far, and sometimes under very specific conditions (e.g., expert samples). Therefore, this study investigates how the three main metacognitive components (metacognitive monitoring, control, and knowledge) contribute to creative performance and behavior. This exploration allows us to address two main questions: Firstly, whether the assumed metacognitive components independently contribute to creative cognitive performance, particularly in divergent thinking (DT) creativity and fluency. Secondly, whether creative metacognition is more strongly related to creative task performance (i.e., DT performance) than to its more remote outcomes of real-life creativity.

Methods

Participants

The final sample consisted of 425 participants (68.5% female, 31.1 % male, 0.5 % other), two-thirds of whom were University students (61.9%). The mean age was 29 years ($M = 28.68$, $SD = 11.29$, range: 18–69 years). We excluded additional participants who either missed any of the attention checks, completed the study too fast (< 1400s) or did not generate at least one response to each divergent thinking task.

Procedure

Participants completed all measures online via *LimeSurvey* November-December 2021. First, they read and confirmed the consent form. All participants were treated following the Declaration of Helsinki. The study procedure had been approved by the ethics committee of University of Graz (GZ. 39/146/63 ex 2020/21). Divergent thinking tasks were completed under "be fluent" and "be creative" instructions, with two task per condition in randomized order per condition. As the study was part of a larger project, participants completed additional tasks that were not in the focus of this work and not described here.

Materials. The data, analyses, and a list of all measures from the study are available in the Open Science Framework (OSF) archive: https://osf.io/7wcdv/?view_only=2b549189101d490d8393e2dbd89b677b.

Measures

Divergent thinking ability. *DT creativity* was assessed as rated creativity of responses in two alternate uses tasks (AUT) in the "be creative" condition. Six independent raters rated all responses on a scale ranging from zero (not creative at all) to four (very creative). One rater was excluded for items 2-4 (but not item 1) to improve inter-rater reliability. The resulting inter-rater reliability was high for all items, ICC between .82 and .83; internal consistency was decent for just two items with Cronbach's alpha = .53. We computed the max-3 score of DT creativity to address the potential confound between the creativity and fluency of responses (Benedek et al., 2013). *DT fluency* was assessed by the total number of generated ideas across two AUT tasks in the "be fluent" condition. Internal consistency for DT fluency was high (Cronbach's alpha = .80).

Creative behavior. *Creative activities* (CACT) were assessed with nine domain-level questions asking the frequency of creative activities during the last 12 months (e.g., in the field of literature writing texts, blog entries, stories etc.; Benedek et al., 2020). We computed a mean score across nine domains (Cronbach's alpha = .64). We also assessed *creative achievements* by asking participants to name their three most creative lifetime achievements (Diedrich et al., 2018). Twelve independent raters examined

these on a scale from zero to five ($ICC = .91$), and we computed a mean score from the resultant ratings across the three achievements (Cronbach's $\alpha = .59$).

Creative metacognitive components.

Metacognition knowledge about creativity was assessed as the breadth of one's creativity conception, assuming that more accurate knowledge about the concept of creativity implies that people recognize that creative ideas can be very diverse, such as magical or unethical (Benedek et al., 2021). This was assessed as the mean endorsement of six possible characteristics of creative ideas (e.g., *magical ideas can be creative e.g., if they would only work in a fantasy world*; all items are listed in the study measures list available in the following OSF link:

https://osf.io/7wcdv/?view_only=2b549189101d490d8393e2dbd89b677b (Cronbach's $\alpha = .77$).

Items were assessed on scale from one (this does not apply at all) to six (this fully applies)".

Metacognitive monitoring of creativity was assessed with the six-item questionnaire of metacognitive feelings in creativity, which captures subjective judgements on the perceived ease and general satisfaction with the creative performance in the preceding DT task (e.g., *I felt that my ideas flowed easily*; Puente-Díaz et al., 2021). Each item was rated on scale from one to seven, with higher values referring to stronger agreement with a statement (Cronbach's $\alpha = .90$).

Metacognitive regulation of creativity was assessed in terms of instruction-related regulation efforts, that is, to adapt task strategy to either focus on the quality of quantity of responses consistent with the current instruction to be creative or fluent, respectively. This was measured as the mean standardized difference in DT creativity between "be creative" and "be fluent" conditions and in DT fluency between "be fluent" and "be creative" conditions. Higher values thus indicate more instruction-congruent performance changes.

Statistical analyses.

To examine how creative metacognitive components (creative metacognitive knowledge, creative metacognitive monitoring, creative metacognitive control) contribute to creative performance and behavior we performed hierarchical multiple regressions. The models tested the relevance of these components for predicting DT creativity and fluency, as well as creative activity and achievements. In all models, step 1 predictor was creativity conception, in step 2 we additionally included metacognitive feelings and in step 3 metacognitive regulation. Furthermore, in models referring to creative behavior, we tested if the relevance of CMC components for creative behavior is (partly) mediated by divergent thinking, by including DT as predictor in step 4. To determine the incremental variance contributed by each predictor at subsequent steps we considered R^2 change (ΔR^2).

We conducted all analyses with jamovi (version 2.3) (The jamovi project, 2022) based on R packages retrieved from MRAN snapshot 2022-01-01) (R Core Team, 2021) and JASP (2023 version 0.17.2.1).

Results

Descriptive statistics and intercorrelations

Both indicators of creative performance, namely creativity and fluency, positively correlate with all subcomponents of creative metacognition, most strongly with metacognitive regulation (CMC control). Creative activity and achievement also show positive associations with several creative metacognitive components albeit less consistently (see Table 1).

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics and Intercorrelations of Variables

	<i>Min</i>	<i>Max</i>	<i>M (SD)</i>	1	2	3	4	5	6
1 DT Creativity	0.167	2.92	1.88 (0.40)						
2 DT Fluency	2.00	25.5	8.69 (3.34)	.497***					
3 Creative activity	0.00	3.56	1.42 (0.59)	.226***	.188***				
4 Creative achievement	0.694	3.28	1.93 (0.40)	.208***	.169***	.172***			
5 MC-K: creative conceptions	0.500	5.00	3.10 (0.96)	.232***	.217***	.099*	.146**		
6 MC-M: metacognitive feelings	0.00	6.00	2.98 (1.09)	.191***	.231***	.323***	.085	.118*	

7 MC-C: metacognitive regulation	-2.32	3.59	0.00 (0.79)	.240***	.348***	-.023	.110*	.073	-.052
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Note. MC-K/M/C = Metacognitive knowledge, monitoring, control
 * p < .05, ** p < .01, *** p < .001

Contributions of creative metacognitive components to creative performance and behavior

To examine contributions of metacognitive components to creative performance and behavior we conducted four hierarchical multiple regressions, one for each of the four creativity measures (DT creativity and fluency, creative activity, and achievements) (see Table 2). To ensure a better comparison of results between analyses, we included the same metacognitive subcomponents in each step, including variables that were not significantly related to creative behavior indicators. To counter violation of assumptions related to non-normality of some variables we report confidence intervals base on 5000 bootstrapping samples.

Table 2

Hierarchical Regression Analysis for Metacognitive Subcomponents Predicting Creative Performance (DT ability) and Behavior (Creative activities and achievements)

	DT Creativity	DT Fluency	Creative activity	Creative achievement
	β [CI _b]	β [CI _b]	β [CI _b]	β [CI _b]
Step 1: MC knowledge				
Creative conceptions	.232*** [0.066, 0.131]	.217*** [0.442, 1.085]	.099* [0.005, 0.121]	.146** [0.025, 0.097]
Adjusted R ²	.052	.045	.008	.019
F (df1, df2)	24.10 (1, 423)***	20.80 (1,423)***	4.22(1, 423)*	9.28 (1, 423)**
Step 2: MC monitoring				
Creative conceptions	.213*** [0.057, 0.122]	.192*** [0.371, 0.994]	.062 [-0.015, 0.093]	.138** [0.022, 0.095]
Metacognitive feelings	.166*** [0.030, 0.097]	.208*** [0.374, 0.879]	.316*** [0.122, 0.218]	.069 [-0.008, 0.058]
Adjusted R ²	0.077	.085	.104	.022
F (df1, df2)	18.6(2, 422)***	20.8 (2,422)***	25.57 (2, 422)***	5.66 (2, 422)**
Δ R ²	.027	.043	.098	.005
Δ F(df1, df2)	12.5 (1, 422)***	19.8 (1, 422)***	46.472 (1, 422)***	2.02 (1, 422)
Step 3: MC control				
Creative conceptions	.194*** [0.052, 0.023]	.164*** [0.282, 0.882]	.063 [-0.016, 0.095]	.130** [0.019, 0.091]
Metacognitive feelings	.181*** [0.034, 0.102]	.230*** [0.460, 0.941]	.315*** [0.124, 0.218]	.075 [-0.005, 0.062]
Metacognitive regulation	.235*** [0.072, 0.165]	.348*** [1.023, 2.008]	-.011 [-0.075, 0.057]	.104* [0.003, 0.100]
Adjusted R ²	.130	.204	.102	.030
F (df1, df2)	22.1(3, 421)***	37.3 (3, 421)***	17.03 (3, 421)***	5.37 (3, 421)**
Δ R ²	.055	.120	.000	.011
Δ F(df1, df2)	26.7(1, 421)***	64.1(1, 421)***	0.06 (1, 421)	4.71 (1, 421)*

Step 4: Creative performance		
Creative conceptions	.022 [-0.042, 0.068]	.094# [0.002, 0.075]
Metacognitive feelings	.271*** [0.098, 0.195]	.038 [-0.019, 0.048]
Metacognitive regulation	-.071 [-0.118, 0.014]	.053 [-0.022, 0.079]
DT Creativity	.151** [0.057, 0.365]	.141* [0.036, 0.240]
DT Fluency	.071 [-0.007, 0.032]	.052 [-0.007, 0.020]
Adjusted <i>R</i> ²	.129	.050
F (df1, df2)	13.51 (5, 419)***	5.44 (5, 419)***
Δ <i>R</i> ²	.031	.024
Δ F(df1, df2)	7.46 (2, 419)***	5.57 (2, 419)**

Note. # *p* < .056, * *p* < .05, ** *p* < .01, *** *p* < .001; Values in square brackets represent 95% confidence intervals of unstandardized regression coefficient *b* based on 5000 bootstrap sample.

All components of metacognition – metacognitive knowledge, monitoring, and control – played independent roles in explaining unique variance of creative cognitive performance, including divergent thinking (DT) creativity and fluency. Among these components, metacognitive control showed the strongest positive association with creative cognitive performance, especially in fluency. In the case of creative behavior, the role of metacognitive subcomponents was less straightforward. Metacognitive knowledge (MC knowledge) positively, though to a small extent, relates to both creative activity and creative achievements. Regarding creative activity, the strongest predictor, the only one that significantly increased the explained variance above MC knowledge, was metacognitive feelings. In the case of creative achievements, metacognitive feelings was not a significant predictor, but instead metacognitive control weakly, positively correlated with them and slightly increased the explained variance above MC knowledge, with both predictors explaining together only around 3% of creative achievement. When divergent thinking was added in the final step of explaining creative behavior, it turns out that the unique contributions of metacognitive components were reduced. While metacognitive feelings still explain a significant unique variance in creative activity, the MC control was no longer significant for creative achievements, suggesting (partial) mediation of the MC effects on creative behavior via DT.

Discussion

Coming up with ideas and creating tangible products, involves goal-oriented actions that require effective resource management. Recently, a theoretical model of creative metacognition was proposed, identifying three main subcomponents supporting core creative cognition: the more static MC knowledge and the more dynamic MC monitoring and control (Lebuda & Benedek, 2023). In the present article, we presented an empirical examination of the framework. The findings provide first evidence that all three postulated components of creative metacognition — metacognitive knowledge, monitoring, and control — played independent roles in creative cognitive performance, as assessed by divergent thinking (DT) creativity and fluency. We further observed contributions of creative metacognitive components to real-life creativity – in terms of creative activities and achievements – although this contribution was relatively limited compared to that for DT performance.

A relationship between **metacognitive knowledge** and divergent thinking has already been demonstrated (van de Kamp et al., 2015). As a new result, we found that broader conception of creativity positively predicts not only DT fluency but also DT creativity as well as creative behavior. Still, the connection is particularly robust when considering fluency, and it seems reasonable. People who embrace that creative ideas can include magical, humorous, and even unethical solutions, may not unnecessarily restrain their thoughts, and instead consider reporting such solutions as they come to mind and even actively search for them, resulting in a significantly greater number of creative ideas. Refraining from dismissing non-standard ideas does not only increase the solution space but may also free cognitive resources that would otherwise be needed to inhibit these candidate responses (Benedek et al., 2012, 2014), which may be one mechanism of how higher idea fluency drives higher idea quality (Forthmann et al., 2021).

The question remains: Why does metacognitive knowledge, measured as a more inclusive definition of creative ideas, also predict creative behavior? It could be speculated that a wider array of

more original ideas could translate into more creative endeavors (Jauk, 2019; Lebeda et al., 2021). Interestingly, we found that metacognitive knowledge explains unique variance in creative behavior above originality of divergent thinking. Here, we cannot dismiss the possibility that this outcome also partly results from the self-descriptive measurement we employed to assess creative activities and achievements. It is likely that a broader conception of creativity also enables a more inclusive classification of diverse types of creative actions. However, validating this hypothesis would necessitate in-depth research for example utilizing thinking-aloud protocols (e.g., Gilhooly et al., 2007; Jankowska et al., 2018).

It is recognized that creative people are doubly skilled, better in generating ideas and also more discerning about the creative quality of their ideas (Silvia, 2008), which corresponds to monitoring at response level. However, our understanding of how metacognitive monitoring at performance level relates to creative performance and especially to creative behavior, remains limited. Here we examined whether an assessment of metacognitive monitoring of the own creative process – metacognitive feelings – incrementally increases creative performance and behavior, beyond metacognitive knowledge. We found that metacognitive feelings together with metacognitive knowledge predicted both facets of divergent thinking: DT creativity and fluency. This finding is consistent with the notion that metacognitive feelings reflects the fluidity of the process, like easiness of ideas' flow, but also the satisfaction with the general process of generating creative ideas (Puente-Díaz et al., 2021).

Interestingly, when metacognitive feelings on divergent thinking performance was added to the model explaining creative activity, the significance of metacognitive knowledge diminished and only monitoring of the creative process predicted creative activity. The contribution of knowledge could be reduced, as we assumed in our model that knowledge supports monitoring, and this pattern although was noticeable although in other creativity measures. Another possible explanation is that creative activity is driven by intrinsic motivation and positive affect (Benedek et al., 2020), which could be related

to the joy and pleasure associated with generating new solutions. Therefore, positive metacognitive feelings associated with the process of generating ideas in everyday life serve as a source for initiating and sustaining creative actions (Benedek et al., 2020; Conner & Silvia, 2015).

In the case of creative achievements, there was no significant relationship with metacognitive feelings. This could be attributed to the characteristic of the previously mentioned metacognitive feelings measurement, which predominantly emphasizes the fluency and ease of idea generation (Puentes-Díaz et al., 2021). Creative achievements demand prolonged effort and a willingness to act despite difficulties – even in the absence of fluency in the process, whether in generating or implementing ideas (Ivcevic et al., 2023; Zielińska et al., 2022). Therefore, it seems that particularly in creative pursuits that yield products acknowledged and valued by the community, self-regulation takes on a notably more prominent role. Within this context, having the skill to tackle challenges (Zielińska et al., 2022) and being well-acquainted with self-motivation tactics (like employing a pep-talk when a creator encounters a hurdle; Ivcevic et al., 2023) may be more relevant than metacognitive abilities.

Adding metacognitive control in the third step of the regression significantly boosted the prediction of creative performance, covering both idea originality and, notably, the quantity of ideas. It's not clear why the role of metacognitive control in fluency appeared even stronger than in the case of originality. We can only speculate that this might be connected to the fact that generating a greater number of ideas requires simpler, readily accessible thinking strategies, such as memory retrieval or self-cueing, rather than generating more creative ideas, which may require findings and implementing more cognitive demanding strategies (e.g., in the context of the AUT disassembly; i.e., breaking an object into parts) (Gilhooly et al., 2007; Jia et al., 2022). Thus, deliberate control might more strongly influence the quantity of generated ideas, as it was easier for the participants to intentionally adapt to the instruction 'be fluent' than to 'be creative.' One might further be concerned that the measure of creative regulation was confounded with the measurement of creative performance as both rely on DT performance.

However, regulation was defined as standardized within-subject changes in individual performance, which should be largely independent of individual differences in performance.

It's worth noting that, in the case of each subcomponent of metacognition (metacognitive knowledge, metacognitive monitoring, and metacognitive control), the relationship appears slightly stronger for fluency compared to the creativity of divergent thinking. This may be linked to different cognitive process complexities associated with generating ideas focused on either the quantity or quality. Alternatively, it is possible that the instruction to generate many ideas is much clearer, and a better understanding of expectations allows for more efficient monitoring and management of idea generation but also allow for more reliable assessment. Yet, this hypothesis needs further examination.

Metacognitive control showed even a slight link to creative achievement, but not to creative activity, and the relation was diminished after adding the creative performance to the model. Creative achievements require original ideas, and proper management of the creative process is crucial to their generation. The lack of this connection between metacognitive control and creative activity might be due to the fact that creative achievements involve a higher degree of cognitive control, which may also support creative self-regulation, as producing works that get noticed, evaluated and appreciated by others necessitates a series of processes regulating the implementation and presentation of a chosen idea (Ivcevic et al., 2023; Zielińska et al., 2022).

Limitations and future directions

As this study first explored the independent contributions of metacognition knowledge, monitoring, and control to creative performance, and creative behavior, it is important to acknowledge the limitations of the study. To start with, the data was collected online. Compared to laboratory research, this introduces limitations in terms of controlling the context, which could be especially relevant to timed performance measures such as divergent thinking tasks. The measurement of metacognitive subcomponents, too, remains open for improvement. First of all, it would be valuable to

employ measurements that go beyond self-report and focus on performance based tests, similar to the approach taken in metacognitive control (Malanchini et al., 2019). We acknowledge that the employed measures may not have directly assessed the accuracy of MC knowledge and the effectiveness of MC monitoring. Future works may aim to devise performance tests for each component or derive them from actual task performance. Moreover, this study only considered MC components at one specific level of granularity (i.e., metacognitive knowledge at the response level, MC monitoring at performance level, and MC control at performance level). Future research thus should aim for assessing MC components at all levels including that of response, performance and task, to provide a more intricate picture of the relationships under investigation. Finally, it would also be worthwhile to closely examine the relationship between creative behavior and metacognition. For this purpose, it could be useful to focus on specific domains of creative activities and achievements. While self-regulation in creativity appears broadly relevant across domains (Zielińska et al., 2023), there is still limited knowledge about metacognition. Certainly, the measurement of creative self-regulation, especially when understood as a trait, should be included as a predictor to ensure that the significance of metacognitive subcomponents incrementally increases the explained variance in creative performance and creative behavior beyond self-regulation. Ultimately, in the presented article, we tested the proposed theoretical model, focusing on the role of individual metacognitive components. In further stages of research, it would be essential to incorporate more dynamic measurements, enabling an analysis of metacognition in the creative process (Lebuda & Benedek, 2023).

Conclusion

The presented research provides novel insights into creative metacognition. We have expanded upon existing studies by incorporating three distinct subcomponents of metacognition – metacognitive knowledge, monitoring, and control – into our measurements. Unlike previous research that predominantly focused on just one aspect, our study offers a more comprehensive approach.

In addition to examining divergent thinking, we also considered the roles played by metacognitive components for creative behavior. As expected, we found that metacognition components more robustly predict creative performance than real-life creativity. We assume that during extensive endeavors that culminate in remarkable and esteemed creative outcomes, self-regulation assumes a notably weightier role. This role extends beyond the mere management of cognitive processes, encompassing the control of other personal and social resources. Nonetheless, these findings represent an initial empirical support of the theoretical framework we had proposed for creative metacognition and further replication and expansion of these results are needed.

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